

LIFE CENTRIC SKILL ENRICHMENT FRAMEWORK - AN EFFECTIVE PEDAGOGY FOR EMPOWERMENT

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Abstract:

India estimates to reach 1.31 billion in terms of population by the end of 2016. The Educational system in the highly populated countries like India should be gender sensitive which impart knowledge along with dissemination of skills to empower the marginalized sections of the society. By facilitating contribution from the marginalized folk, the country can move further towards prosperity in near future. The dissemination of knowledge and building competency for the common good are the two faces of empowerment. Life centric skill enrichment framework is an effective model named 'Pradeep's Model of Life Centric Skill Enrichment' developed by Prof. Pradeep M.D. highlighting various Life Skills needed for the people to face challenges in her life span. Every person should continuously grow and develop in their life to be self sufficient in the society. Empowerment of people through skill enrichment can reduce their miseries to a great extent. This model is framed as per the life expectancy of men estimated at the age of 64 years and for women at the age of 69.6 years as fixed by the Union Ministry of Health and Family Welfare in India during 2015. This framework considers four phases for the skill development in human life span. Firstly, Early Adulthood (until 12 years) a Reception stage for the Basic Skills, Secondly, Adolescence (12-18 years) a Stage of Analysis for the Advanced skills, thirdly, Adult & Middle Age (18-60 years) a Practice stage for Projective Skills and lastly, Old age (Later 60 years to death) a Projection stage for Self sustaining skills. This model can be adopted as a value addition to the formal education system of the country to build competency which can empower people further.

Index Terms: Women, Education, Skill, Life Centric, Psychosocial & Life Span

1. Introduction:

According to Pradeep M.D. (2016) human beings does every action by using their mind with the help of memory by detecting the most needed information from the pool of existing information's. Knowledge determines the ways to adopt, use and control physical and social changes. The application of knowledge after critically analyzing the results of each action will derive wisdom. This application for different purposes depends upon the skill of that person. Education is one of the modes to improve skills among people to contribute for the national growth. In spite of more schools, universities and technical institute's people are lacking with many needed skills. The factors such as Poverty, Inflation etc. prohibit the poor from gaining required skills. Basil Hans V. & Sowjanya S Shetty (2016) Skill based training will be an important milestone towards people's empowerment to bring change from the traditional outset to the modern outlook. As backward and weaker sections of the society are the victims of exploitation, building competency helps in acquiring better livelihood by improving the status in the society. India can enrich further through the contributions of weaker sections such as women, children, youths and elderly. Erik Erikson E. H (1993) has given Psychosocial theory of development stating the effects of external factors, parents and society upon development of personality by identifying eight stages in life such as Infancy (Birth- 18 Months), Early Childhood (18 Months to 3 Years), Preschooler (3 to 5 Years), School Age (6 to 12 Years), Adolescent (12 to 18 Years), Young adult (18 to 35), Middle-aged (35 to 55) & Late Adult (55 to Death).

2. Pradeep Model of Life Centric Skill Enrichment:

Empowerment strategy should improve the knowledge and skills of people for enabling them to contribute towards national progress. This model is based on the accepted life expectancy by the Union Ministry of Health and family welfare in India (2011-15). The World Health Organization defines life expectancy as the average number of years a person is expected to live according to the current mortality rates in the present health status of the population. Life Centric Skill Enrichment Model focuses to improve the skills among the people to empower them in life. This model divides skill enrichment process into four stages such as reception, analysis, adoption and projection which definitely empower the people to a great extent if it is provided along with the formal education system. The flow chart diagram of this model is shown in Fig. 1.

3. Techniques used in the Model:

(a) Supportive Formal System: The Ministry of Human Resource Development (1985) introduced universalisation of education. National Policy on Education (1986) aimed equity by removing the disparities after meeting the needs of educationally backward sections. National Literacy Mission (1988) to tackle the problem of illiteracy. Mahila Samakhya Programme (1988) recognized education as the tool for empowerment.

Joint Council for Vocational Education (1990) to monitor the Vocational Training Programmes. Action Scheme of Support to Voluntary Agencies for Adult Education and Skill Development (1992). National Council for Teachers Education (1995) established as a statutory body. The National Plan of Action for the Girl Child (1991-2000) framed to protect and promote the Girl Child. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (2000-2001) to provide universal education by eliminating the gender gap in the elementary education. National Policy for the Empowerment of Women (2001), Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (2004) residential schools at upper primary for girls belonging to SC, ST, OBC and Minorities for educationally backward blocks.

Figure 1: 'Pradeep Model of Life Centric Skill Enrichment'

National Curriculum Framework (2005) to frame a common curriculum for all. Model School Scheme (November 2008) constituting 6,000 schools affiliated to CBSE Board for the education of talented Rural Children. Saakshar Bharat (Sept 2009) to raise the literacy rate to 80%. Right to Education Act (April 2010) by The Constitution (Eighty-sixth Amendment) Act, 2002 inserted Free and Compulsory Education of all children

between the age group of 6 to 14 years under the (Article 21-A) of Indian Constitution as a Fundamental Right. The Scheme of Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (2016) for preventing gender based sex selection and encouraging education. Pradeep M.D. (July 2016) according to Government of India census survey report, the literacy rate grew from 18.33 % (1951), to 28.30 % (1961), 34.45 % (1971), 43.57 % (1981), 52.21 % (1991), 64.84 % (2001) to 74.04 % during (2011). Overall Literacy rate increased by 9.2 % from 64.84 % prevailed in 2001 to 74.04 % in 2011. Female literacy rate increased by 10.97 % from 53.67 % prevailed in 2001 to 64.64 % in 2011. Number of illiterates (7+ age group) decreased from 304.10 million prevailed in 2001 to 282.59 million in 2011. Gender disparity in literacy rates declined by 5.34 % points from 21.59 % prevailed in 2001 to 16.25 % in 2011.

(b) Consistent Learning Pedagogy: According to Pradeep M.D. (August 2015) Skills can be oriented by participatory method of teaching in which knowledge and methods are neutral to each other. The trainer will help the participants to detect the self known techniques and challenge the pre-conceptions to gain new attributes. The social transformation is possible only through the critical analysis of the situation by the process of condensing, rebuilding and inculcation of different stimuli. Participants experience is the main source of information in this method. The trainers are just mentors who are partners in learning. Group exercise and self learning makes the learning more interesting. Motivation by the mentor plays a very important role in learning skills along with regular evaluation and follow up. The mentor guides to take training notes and motivate the participants to go through the notes every day. Absolute liberty is provided to clarify the doubts. This method will improve the analytical skill of the learner and mentoring skill of the mentor simultaneously.

(c) Discarding the Social Stigma: The status of weaker sections are unfavorable, even though they constitute the marginalised majority. A girl child suffers from discrimination both before and after birth for food, education, health care, employment, social status and decision making authority in the family. According to Anju Bhatia (2000) specially, women carry dual burden by involving in less quantifiable domestic works like cooking, fetching water, sending children to school, feed the cattle, milking cow and helping the family occupations like agriculture, pottery, poultry, animal husbandry etc. Women suffer from many disadvantages when compared to men, hence it is necessary to address social and economic deprivations. The issues of Gender bias, discrimination, domestic confinement, social restrictions, poor health services, malnutrition, lack of education and employment, political exclusion, low status, violence, migration, changes in labour market, need to be treated with new skills, to meet the constitutional commitment. The social stigma about the weaker sections should be eliminated from the society. "Beti Bachao Beti Padhao" is a major initiative taken in 2015 to tackle this problem by the central government. The government started mainstreaming women by granting equal status with men by embodying several legislations & policies. As illiteracy reduces self confidence, competency and self reliance among the people, the need for social, economic and political empowerment of weaker sections by education and skill development is the need of the day. Pradeep M.D (February 2016) The process of empowerment is conceptualized to build personal assertions, self-esteem, confidence, self protection, active political participation (political empowerment), enrich education (social empowerment), eliminating gender barriers in employment (economic empowerment), legal awareness (legal empowerment) and autonomy in the family (Domestic empowerment).

(d) Framework for Skill Delivery Model: The framework of skill delivery depends upon the age of the participants and existing virtue as per the psychosocial development. Skill delivery is done upon the need of the participants according to the age through the various identified skills for competency building. (Refer Table-1).

Table-1: Framework for Skill Delivery Model

Stages	Age	Virtue	Key Skills	Traits
Reception	Early Childhood (Until 11 Years)	Desire & Creativity	Basic Skills	Play, Literacy, Autonomy and Talent
Analysis	Adolescence (12-18 Years)	Autonomy	Advanced Skills	Special Skills, Career Guidance and Life Skills
Adoption	Adult & Middle Age (19-59 Years)	Maturity	Projective Skills	Parenting, Soft Skill, Research & Entrepreneurship
Projection	Old age (60 Years-Death)	Sacrifice	Sustenance Skills	Self Reliance

(e) Web Based Training: It represents learning opportunities beyond the entry-level degree to enable the women to increase their skill, proficiency and knowledge. Consortiums like NPTEL, Edx etc. are providing short term skill development programmes. According to Pradeep M.D. & Krishna Prasad K. (April 2016) It is a self directed process to assume responsibility for professional development. Examples of technology based continuing education is provided through internet to include any courses, lectures, seminars which are mediated by technology to include computer-based training, online courses, Web based or satellite televised workshops/seminars. The free, online classes do not typically award credit but, provides students access to skill development at higher education. The standard classes are offered to different skills along with access to real course materials, assignments, essays, readings, videos and lectures. All the classes can be completed at the

student's own pace, with the freedom of study. Online study clubs gives students a chance to form groups and virtually study and converse with fellow classmates.

(f) Skill Development Module: According to Pradeep M.D. & Aithal P.S. (September, 2015) The dialogical approach of learning is characterized by cooperation and acceptance in the roles of teacher and learner. It demands an atmosphere of mutual acceptance and trust. In this method, all will teach and all will learn. As without dialogue there is no communication. Libaratory education is possible only after creating a good learning environment. For ‘Skill Development Module’ (Refer Table 2).

Table 2: Training Module

Age Criterion	Type of Skill	Key Traits	Agency	Subject
Early Childhood (Until 12 Years)	Basic Skills	Play	Family & Play Schools	Letters, Poems, Games etc.
		Literacy	School	Writing, Reading and Using Numbers
		Autonomy	Family	Toilet Training, Ironing, Table Manners, Cleaning and Hygiene, Religious Orientation (Prayer, God, Beliefs etc.)
		Talent	School	Singing, Dancing, Writing, Painting, Playing, Drawing, crafts work, Sports & Games, Marshal Arts, Instruments etc.
Adolescence (12 to 18 Years)	Advanced Skills	Special Skills	Family & Coaching Centres	Swimming, Cycling, Computer Proficiency, Cooking, Banking, Domestic Works (Painting, Plumbing, Gardening, Cleaning etc) Self Defense, Cycling etc.
		Career Guidance	Consultants	Career Options, Courses available, Institutions, Scholarships, Infrastructure, Bank Loan etc.
		Life Skills	Institutions & Colleges	Negotiation Skills, Employability Skills, Leadership, Presentation Skills, Time Management, Organising Skills, Fund raising and Management, Conflict Resolution, Stress Management etc.
Adulthood & Middle Age (18-60 Years)	Projective Skills	Domestic Skills	Institutions	Parenting, Sex Education, Health and Nutrition, Yoga & Meditation, Habit Management
		Soft Skill	College, Institutions & Training Centres	Communication, Decision Making, Commitment, Flexibility, Creativity, Team Work, Motivation, Inter personal Skills, Negotiation, Monitoring etc.
		Research Skill	Research Centers	Literature Review, Data Collection, Publication, Data Analysis and Reporting
		Entrepreneurial Skills	Vocational Training Institutes	Driving, Tailoring, Mobile Technolgy, Domestic Products, Branding, Marketing, Social Networking, Quality Management etc.
Old Age (Later 60 Years to Death)	Self Sustaining Skills	Self Reliance Skills	NGO's and Day Care Centres	Stigma Ventilation, Healthy Life Style, Managing the Earnings etc.

(g) Group Intervention: Pradeep M.D. & Rakshitha Rai R. P. (January 2016) Non Governmental organizations (NGOs), Community Based Organizations and government have recognized Self Help Groups (SHGs) to address the specific needs and problems of rural people. This group comprises a chair person, deputy, treasurer and other office holders. It will disseminate information, try to upgrade skills and links the members with financial institutions. Credits are offered through the regular savings deposited by the members weekly or fortnightly. Loans for short term are offered to the members for productive purposes. These Micro credit and other activities will help for the social and economic development of the marginalized.

(h) Crash Course: Short term courses are offered by various institutions at a fixed fee. These specialized courses aim to develop the particular skill of the participants within the prescribed duration. The duration may vary from a week to one month. Recently flexible timings are offered with evening and week end classes to encourage the working people also. It includes short courses on Swimming, Resource Mobilisation, Counselling, Disaster Management, Cooking, Parenting, Yoga & Meditation, Nutrition, Spoken English, Research Methodology, Legal Education, Computer training, etc. The trainer can use the ‘Pradeep Consistence Learning Model’ to improve the slow learners who have registered for the course. This method is a mutual learning for both learner and trainer.

(i) Career & Legal Training: Pradeep M.D. (February 2015) It enables the rural poor to earn their own livelihood by promoting micro enterprises to face the market changes with needed skills and abilities. The members with no educational, industrial or entrepreneurial background were made to be self dependent and self reliant. It aims to enhance the decision making capacity, build strength and confidence to solve problems. Special skills like Driving, Tailoring, Mobile service, Manufacturing Domestic Products, Branding, Marketing, Social Networking, Quality Management etc are also provided. Prime Minister Narendra Modi launched Skill India campaign in this regard. The task of empowerment always should guarantee freedom, status and dignity under the umbrella of justice. The legal empowerment through legal education, public interest litigation, legal aid programmes shall be adopted.

(j) Research Training: Weaker section must be motivated to engage in research at higher education. Opportunities shall be given for the publication of research findings in reputed National and International Journals. More students should be trained to clear NET/SLET examinations to qualify for Research Fellowships. Available scholarships for the minorities and backward communities should be informed. Research skills needed for Literature Review, Data Collection, Publication, Data Analysis and Reporting should be developed through the Research Methodology workshops and seminars. Build skills to use SPSS Software. Conference shall be organized at colleges to inculcate research behavior among the youth.

(k) Geriatric Welfare: Pradeep M. D. & Charan Raj (July 2016) Elderly people are increasing in India due to the decline in fertility rate and Mortality rate. In developed regions, approximately one person for every six persons is at the age of 60 years which may reach one person for every four persons by 2025. This is the age of decline functional capacity of the human organs due to physiological transformation in the life cycle. The study of physical and psychological changes that occur in old age is called “gerontology”. It is presumed that 177 million population will be geriatrics by 2025. Despite advances in health care, many elders are suffering from chronic, incurable and progressive diseases. They are facing tensions to prevent physical disability to extend the "active life expectancy". Fortunately, recent studies suggest that healthy aging is achievable, with sound planning for old age. Illnesses like diabetes, mellitus, congestive heart failure, and some forms of dementia can be delayed or even prevented. A positive attitude to overcome illness and personal losses to face the life effectively. They should focus to protect physical and mental health by adopting a healthy life style. They can be trained in facing post retirement stigma, utilization of retirement benefits, day care, health, nutrition etc..

4. Merits of the Model:

(a) Authoritative Development: This model will ensure the overall development of the participants in all the spheres of life to compete and cope with challenges of life. This will enrich the competency to compete in occupation and professions to improve the status generally. The empowerment will improve the confidence to deal the domestic and professional responsibilities better. People can improve the different skills on requirement hence works as the need based training pedagogy.

(b) Empowerment: The need for empowerment is essential to prevent exploitation and discriminations which is invading upon the right to life and privacy of people. The issues of violence, cruelty, sexual assaults, harassments and oppressions need to be controlled. The right to life is guaranteed at the threshold of social justice to all. Empowerment is a process of creating awareness about social realities and rights, to build capacity through education and skill development to compete with the change. Participation in savings and economic development will improve the status. This model tries to change the nature and direction of systems affecting under privileged and other disadvantaged sections in the society.

(c) Pro-Health: The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines health as “A state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing which is essential for leading a productive life, which is not merely the absence of disease or infirmity”. People are facing high risk of malnutrition, retardation, diseases, disability and death during infancy, early childhood, adolescence, reproductive age and old age. This model will generate health awareness among the people at various ages according to the need.

(d) Political Participation: The political participation includes voting, supporting the political groups, communication with the legislators, dissemination of political views and opinions among the electorates and other allied activities. Political participation always involves an organized activity that affects the power relationships in the society. Political participation not only includes the activities which formally empower the people to make decisions but also the intension to influence the attitudes and behavior of those people who have powers for decision making. The empowered people can effectively participate in political activities.

(e) Social Status: Social empowerment is a process in which awareness is created about the status to build self-confidence through critical thinking. The Economic development through skill development will encourage the people towards self employment which improve the social status.

(f) Autonomy: Economic empowerment is possible by developing vocational and technical skills by providing training to income generation activities based on their need. The opening up of the economy and rapid economic growth in the last five years has increased the existing structural barriers by introducing furthermore new challenges. As Economic development creates more jobs in the industrial and service sectors which improves the autonomy and self dependency among people.

(g) Domestic Competency: The micro credit is one of the solutions to promote the quality of life to accelerate the socio-economic development by reducing the rural poverty considerably. Self Help Groups (SHGs) are mostly informal groups which follow the framed rules to satisfy common goals by collective effort. It plays an important role in maintaining domestic responsibilities by mutual support from the members of the family.

(h) Inclusive Growth: Indian economy is growing across the world. The country remain shackled with evils like corruption, social barriers, violence against women, deprivation of the minorities. Growth is not uniform across the sectors as many cross-sections of the populae remain outside the process of development. Several social, political and economic factors need to be tackled for sustaining the inclusive growth. Inclusive growth is “a growth process which yields broad-based benefits by ensuring equal opportunity for all”. It concentrates equitable allocation of resources with benefits accruing to every section of society. It is concerned with the Pro-poor growth and growth with equity. This model contributes for inclusive growth of all towards prosperity.

5. Demerits of the Model:

(a) Migration: Migration in India is more due to the pattern of employment. People migrate from one place to the other in search of better jobs. The skill development programme will be affected through this migration of families. Creating a uniform system of skill development delivery system is a challenge which has to be met in this regard. Proper network between the service delivery agencies need to be established.

(b) Social and Religious Constraints: The socialization takes place in the family. Women is constrained to perform the dependency role after her marriage. Social constraints force the women to maintaining family. The factors like marriage, role in the family will affect the people from getting the fruits of this model fully. Typically, the orthodox mindset in the Indian society makes it difficult for the woman to balance her domestic responsibilities along with the skill development initiatives.

(c) Cost: This model is expensive as there is a huge expenditure for training these skills. There is a need for infrastructure, Teaching Faculties, Proper Curriculum, process of authenticity for the modules. Proper financial support should be done to improve the training modules in order to be sustainable.

(d) Lack of Trained Professionals: Skills can be trained by an expert. The adoption of this model strictly may give rise for the scarcity of Trainers. If the intensity of the course is reduced then it may affect the quality of the module. There is a chance that good trainers may charge more and more fee.

6. Conclusion:

According to Pradeep M.D (February 2016) Indian economy is progressive at the global phase in spite of certain social backlogs like corruption, normative social structure, social evils, violence against women, depriving the down trodden minority. Overall development and growth is not uniform across all the sectors of the society. Large mass has been kept outside the development strategies. Social, political and economic protocol has to be monitored which ensure sustainable development assuring greatest welfare to the nation. A uniform and common growth strategy shall implement and accelerate the deprived. Formulation of common developmental plan which is unique may bypass the diversities of incredible India. This type of inclusive growth strategy shall create a platform for the broader benefits by emphasizing equality in allocating the resources, providing opportunities and services to every section of the society. Vision is kept highly on the pro-poor growth of the deprived. In Social structure men were kept unjustifiably superior which planted paternal bias, powerlessness and dependence of women. It boosted opportunities for vulnerability and crimes against women in the society. Collective efforts should be put by the government, Non Governmental Organisation's, Educational Institutions, Training Centers, Tutorials towards effective delivery of Life centric skill enrichment programmes specified in the module to empower the people to the fullest. Establishment of the formal policy framework from the government to support this model by the government will be a great effort in this regard.

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